

A complex network diagram with black lines, nodes, and colored diamonds (orange, red, green, blue) is overlaid on a light gray background. The diagram is partially obscured by the text and the orange footer.

Report on the influence of situational variables and personal networks on online resilience and digital skills

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Report on the influence of situational variables and personal networks on online resilience and digital skills

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AIM

To explore how peer networks affect digital skills among children and adolescents.

STEP BY STEP

123 networks (school classes), nested in 15 different schools (total of 2,562 students).

Observed networks of friendship, digital advice seeking and digital advice giving. Taking into account individual and multiple networks.

WHERE

Germany, Italy,
and Portugal

WHEN

1st wave of ySKILLS
school survey
Spring 2021

FRIENDSHIP NETWORKS

In some classes, the adolescents' networks show dispersed and clearly delineated subnetworks without relationships between each other (A). In others, the networks are denser and interconnected (B).

Examples of classes and subnetworks observed.

The school classes observed have networks of a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 32 students.

KEY FINDINGS

Gender importance

Students of the **same gender** tend to disproportionately **be friends**, tend to **ask advice** in matters of digital technology, as well as **seek advice** with each other.

Specific skills on giving and seeking advice

An adolescent with a **high digital skill** level is often **asked for advice** and frequently **provides advice** to peers.

Proficiency in digital skills

Students tend to **ask for advice** and **seek advice** from other students with a **similar proficiency** in digital skills.

An adolescent with **low digital skill** level frequently **seeks and receives** a high amount of advice from others.

Advice giving and advice seeking are probably by nature characterised by **seeking social approval** and **confirmation**.

However, **advice network ties** were more common among children or adolescents with **different school performance levels**.

Some adolescents are **super helpers** since their expertise does potentially travel through classrooms.

1. Executive summary

This report presents first insights into the relationships between youth social structures and digital skills, with a special emphasis on peer networks. Based on unique socio-centric network data collected across school classes in three different countries it does provide a fresh perspective on how to integrate peer networks into the analyses of youth digital skills. Structures of peer networks arguably can be an important and effective explanatory factor for adolescents' digital skills. The report emphasises the advantages of collecting sociocentric network data.

The report discusses three subtypes of peer networks as adolescents' social structure – a friendship network, and two (digital skills-related) advice giving and advice seeking networks.

The report considers to what degree expertise in digital skills would cause homophily in the peer friendship network, and to what degree the structures of advice giving and advice seeking networks would be related to youths' digital skills.

The report provides novel methodological insights into modelling a larger set of sociotropic network data. First, it shows that missing data imputation is central before network estimations and that a multiple imputation approach is most appropriate for substantial amounts of missing data. Second, it shows that for analysing multiple network data – if the data is known to come from different distributions and there is information on the group affiliation of each individual network – an hierarchical grouped approach is the optimal choice.

The substantial results show that digital skills play only a minor role in network homophily, where sociodemographics, in particular gender, have much stronger effects. Moreover, the results demonstrate very clear and consistent network effects in which giving advice and being sought for advice is related to more digital proficiency, while seeking advice and being given advice is related to less advanced digital skills.

1 Introduction

1.1 The ySKILLS project

The ySKILLS (Youth Skills) project is funded by the European Union (EU's) Horizon 2020 programme. It involves 16 partners from 13 countries to enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the information and communications technology (ICT) environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for children and young people by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills. Starting from the view that children are **active agents in their own development**, ySKILLS examines how digital skills mediate the risks and opportunities related to ICT use by 12- to 17-year-olds in Europe (see <https://yskills.eu>).

The overarching aim of ySKILLS

To enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the ICT environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for all children by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills.

ySKILLS will **identify the actors and factors** that undermine or can promote **children's wellbeing** in a digital age. The relations between ICT use and wellbeing will be critically and empirically examined over time.

ySKILLS' research objectives

To acquire extensive knowledge and better measurement of digital skills.

To develop and test an innovative, evidence-based explanatory and foresight model predicting the complex impacts of ICT use and digital skills on children's cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing.

To explain how at-risk children (as regards their mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender) can benefit from online opportunities despite their risk factors (material, social, psychological).

To generate insightful evidence-based recommendations and strategies for key stakeholder groups in order to promote European children's digital skills and wellbeing.

This report contributes to achieving the second objective of ySKILLS by focusing on how ICT use and skills impact children's wellbeing and cognitive functions. More specifically, this report presents the findings on structural effects of networks and their impact on the interplay of ICT use and skills and wellbeing.

ySKILLS has proposed, and will continue to develop, its **conceptual model** (see Figure 1):

1.2 This report

This report takes a focus on social structures affecting digital skills among children and adolescents, with a special emphasis on peer networks. It discusses that structures of peer network arguably can be an important and effective explanatory factor for adolescents' digital skills, and provides a rationale for more thoroughly considering peer networks as important factors in young people's social structures. It then continues to discuss how a network perspective on peer influences should be an important step in informing research on the effects of social structures, also in more general terms. Specifically, in this report we discuss three subtypes of peer networks as adolescents' social structure – a friendship network, and two (digital skills-related) advice giving and advice seeking networks. We are interested to what degree expertise in digital skills would cause homophily in the peer friendship network, and to what degree the structures of advice giving and advice seeking networks would be related to youths' digital skills. The report provides information about how network data on peer influences was collected among children and adolescents in the framework of the ySKILLS school survey and highlights the value of sociocentric network data. Before moving into the results regarding peer influences, the deliverable provides an extensive methodological discussion of the difficulties in modelling and analysing the collected network data. The results show that digital skills play only a minor role in network homophily. Moreover, the results demonstrate very clear and consistent network effects in which giving advice and being sought for advice is related to more digital proficiency, while seeking advice and being given advice is related to less advanced digital skills.

2 Networks and youth digital skills

In contemporary societies, digital skills have become central to successfully navigate personal, civic and professional life and to avoid growing digital inequalities (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2011). In that sense, acquiring or holding digital skills has been shown to relate to peoples' sense of well-being (e.g., Livingstone, Mascheroni & Stoilova, 2021; Vissenberg, d'Haenens & Livingstone, 2022), but also to educational goal attainment (e.g., Pagani et al., 2016) or to a more favourable positioning on the labour market (e.g., Kiss, 2017). In a world that is increasingly percolated with digital technology and in which more and more daily life activities are relying upon having access to and mastering such technology, the role of digital skills is unlikely to diminish. By digital skills we here align with the definition used throughout the ySKILLS project and refer to the Telecommunication Union's (ITU) definition of digital skills as people's "ability to use ICTs in ways that help individuals to achieve beneficial, high-quality outcomes in everyday life for themselves and others" and to "reduce potential harm associated with more negative aspects of digital engagement" (2018, p.23).

To prepare young people for life in a digitalising world, it is indispensable to cater for digital skills development. The phases of childhood and adolescence are now being affected more by the use of technology than ever before (Danby et al., 2018). Whether it is the use or acquisition of smartphones and tablets in early childhood or the use of computers and whiteboards in educational contexts, young people are regularly confronted with technology. Yet, training in digital skills differs and depends on a range of factors. Before coming to briefly discuss factors that would make some children and adolescents hold more digital skills than others, it is important to note that the conceptualisation and consequently the operationalisation of digital skills do differ between studies and approaches and is not universally agreed upon (for an elaborate discussion, see [ySKILLS D2.1](#), pp. 25-29). It is striking that there is little in the way of conceptual differentiation of skills for different age groups, and the target object of the skills – the digital – is understood in very broad and diverse terms. Also, there is little agreement in the way that skills can be subjective, self-report assessments of perceived skills or can be measured through more objective performance testing. It is important to take into account this diversity of concepts and measures when understanding the diversity and sometimes contradictory or unclear nature of empirical findings in the extant literature. Our conceptualisation and measurement of digital skills then follows the ySKILLS projects' approach, differentiating five dimensions of digital skills in the [youth Digital Skills Indicator](#) (yDSI): (1) technical and operational skills, (2) programming skills, (3) information navigation and processing skills, (4) communication and interaction skills, and (5) content creation and production skills.

Children's and adolescents' online resilience has been shown to critically depend on holding digital skills. Online resilience, usually defined as the ability to cope with risky or negative online experiences and show problem-solving competencies to avoid further harm (e.g., Vandoninck et al., 2013), appears to be stronger when certain competences and skills are more developed. How skills and resilience develop and influence each other over time, however, is less clear. Given that this report provides initial evidence focusing on cross-sectional network data, we only consider skills as outcome variables. Subsequent steps will engage with a longitudinal perspective as to how skills are causally related to resilience.

Given the centrality of digital skills in the early life phase, a considerable amount of empirical studies have engaged with the question why some children and adolescents have higher digital skills levels than others (for a comprehensive review, see [ySKILLS D2.1](#)). These studies, usually conducted within the confines of a particular country or context, have considered a range of different types of digital skills and usually rely on survey-based or experimental methodological approaches. In sum, it appears that some factors consistently show a relationship with children and adolescents acquiring or

holding digital skills. Among these main factors identified in prior literature are education, extensive use of digital technologies, age and gender. As seems very plausible, older children tend to have better digital skills. Gender appears to be a factor in self-reported skill levels, with boys claiming to hold better skills. This finding, however, is not replicated in actual performance tests. Both better cognitive skills but also better academic achievements appear to be related to higher digital skills. Finally, also quite plausible, it has been shown that positive attitudes towards digital technologies also relate to holding better digital skills.

As evident from the short reviews above, there is a stronger focus on looking at individual capacities rather than contextual aspects. Yet, children and adolescents are embedded in multiple social structures (Jenks, 2004) and it is reasonable to assume that these social embeddings do reflect on the acquisition, maintenance, and sharing of digital skills. In particular, given that digital skills training is often not structurally and elaborately integrated into formal educational programs, and digital skills acquisition often comes from informal sources (e.g., Karuovic, 2016), social structures may play an integral role for skill acquisition. Such a social structural perspective, which departs from the commonly more individually focused perspective on adolescents' digital skills acquisition, joins more recent literature in the field that emphasises the role of networks and spaces when it comes to peoples' engagement with digital technologies (Helsper, 2021). Yet, this is not to say that social structures have been ignored thus far. Extant literature does provide rationales and insights on three types of social structures by means of looking at the impact of factors related to family contexts and schools, and to a lesser extent to peer networks (see also [ySKILLS D2.1](#), pp. 61-73).

This report takes a particular focus on peer networks. It argues that the relative paucity of an empirical focus on peer influences on digital skills is an important gap in the current literature, given the centrality of peers in many young peoples' lives and given that peers may provide for very different kinds of learning resources than parents or schools, such as providing available opportunity structures of seeking and providing relevant expertise in terms of digital skills. Individual skill differences between peers due to some of the individual factors outlined above may spread through peer networks in terms of social learning and by means of using technologies together. Yet whether those dynamics do occur and how they occur is unclear thus far. Relatedly, the role of seeking advice from others and conversely, the role of giving advice to others has not been the central subject of extant research. The network data collected in the framework of the ySKILLS project is unique, in that they not only take seriously notions of peer networks, but also go beyond an egocentric perspective on peer influences. As elaborated below, the data collection allowed us to gather information not only about the individual reporting to give or seek advice (ego), but also about the individual that is reported to seek or give advice (alter) and whether such relationships are mutual. Hence at the centre of interest of this report is the question whether peer networks, above and beyond more established individual and contextual factors, do add to our understanding of the acquisition and development of digital skills, and if so, what network properties would explain such dynamics.

The report is structured as follows. First, below, we briefly discuss both the nature of digital skills and the possible influences of social structures on skills acquisition among young people. We then discuss the potential added value of a network perspective on peer influences. After briefly describing the data, we move into an elaborate discussion of the methodological challenges in the analysis of the network data. Finally, we provide a series of results and put these into perspective in a short discussion.

2.1 Social structure and children's and adolescents' digital skills

As outlined above, it is increasingly acknowledged that the social structures in which children and adolescents grow up may determine differences in digital skills levels above and beyond individual resources. In the literature acknowledging social structures, the main focus is on the influence of *family structures*. Differences in the contexts that families provide for supposedly would bear on the development of skills. Prior studies have for instance shown that the socio-economic status (SES) of parents in terms of education levels, household incomes or parents' occupations does relate to children's skill levels (for a summary, see [D2.1](#), p. 61). Overall, the existing evidence points towards the fact that higher parental or family SES is positively related to skill levels. Hence children and adolescents growing up in families in which parents have high education levels, are earning comparatively well or have highly skilled jobs tend to have more digital skills. Yet the evidence appears to be somewhat mixed, depending on the actual measurement of SES or on the type of digital skills that were looked at. Another factor important to the development of digital skills that is related to the context that is provided for by the family is parental mediation of the use of digital media and resources (for a summary, see [D2.1](#), p. 63). Here the literature distinguishes between enabling mediation, which refers to parents talking to children about what they are doing online, enabling online activities or and giving advice as to how to safely navigate online environments, and restricting mediation, which basically relates to limiting the time of usage of digital technologies (Livingstone et al., 2017). Overall, the literature suggests that enabling mediation has a positive influence on skill acquisition, while restrictive mediation largely has a negative impact. Hence, a restriction of the usage time of children's use of digital technology is likely to cause lower skill levels. The type of parental mediation again depends on the socio-economic characteristics of parents and their own use of digital technologies. The latter factor also shows some direct effects on adolescents' skills. In sum we see that family structure does have substantial explanatory power for whether and to what degree adolescents acquire digital skills, although the overall picture is somewhat mixed.

The *school environment* does form yet another important type of social structure that has been at the focus of a number of prior studies. Children and adolescents spend substantial amounts of time in school, and these could have an important function in levelling out differences caused by family backgrounds. As outlined in [D2.1](#) (pp. 66-69) it appears useful to distinguish between factors that relate to teachers, to the types of information about and experiences with information and communication technology (ICT) that students have at school and to the school environment itself. There is only marginal evidence suggesting that teachers' attitudes towards and skills related to ICT use have an effect on school children. If teachers do have positive attitudes and good skills, they probably still need a school environment that would enable them to draw on such resources. Overall, the experiences with ICT in a school environment tend to be positively related to digital skills, yet the evidence is not uniformly pointing into this direction. Thus, generally the literature supports the usefulness of schools making investments into integrating ICT experiences for their students. Finally, school-related variables were not found to have a consistent positive effect on students' digital skills, and findings do not go much beyond showing that differences between schools do exist. Again, while it is reasonable to assume that the social structure offered in schools would be an important factor, the available evidence is mixed, at best.

While the number of prior studies considering the influences of family or school related variables is at least substantial, there is rather little research thus far looking at the effects of *peers* on digital skills acquisition. Indeed there may be partial overlaps in school and peer effects, but in the way that school effects have been theorised and investigated, there is a stronger focus on teachers and curricula. But adolescence is a time in which strong ties with peers are developed and maintained and peers form an important part of adolescents' daily interactions. The potential for peer interactions is also

increased through the digital environment. Yet the literature on digital skills thus far has shown only very little systematic engagement with the role of peers for digital skills. Extant studies that have looked at peer influences (for an overview see [D2.1](#), p. 70) paint an overall positive picture. Peers seem to be helpful in terms of informally teaching and learning digital skills from each other and hence passing on or co-developing skills. Using digital technologies together with peers does promote digital skills and this seems to be even more pronounced when doing so with close friends. While the existing evidence appears to uniformly point into the direction of a positive influence of peers, it appears fundamental to gain a better understanding of peer influence above and beyond what was established so far. Who do children and adolescents turn to when seeking or giving advice about digital technologies? And do advice networks matter for the development of digital skills? In sum these questions demand understanding peer influences from the perspective of a network logic. Particularly schools ensure that children and adolescents have a multitude of regular social contacts (which could be further extended through leisure time activities) and are embedded in peer networks. This deliverable seeks to shed new light on the actual network processes that are at play when it comes to peer effects on digital skills.

Peer networks and their influences so far have been considered primarily in terms of adolescents' digital activities. The basic argument is that social structures, such as professional, family or peer networks can, through the skills needed and present in such structures, either foster or inhibit the learning of digital skills. In other words, such peer structures can promote social learning, by means of passing on knowledge and skills from one member to the next within the peer network. But they can also have normative influences on the individuals that are embedded in the peer networks in terms of creating a normative need for individuals in the network to obtain skills. When such networks contain individuals with expert knowledge or high skill levels, these can be assumed to spread through the networks as purposeful learning efforts, taking into account the closeness of expert knowledge, or as incidental learning through the co-use of technologies. Peer networks that are to some degree characterised by the usage of or reliance on digital technologies may also lead less skilled individuals to uptake skills that thus appear to be normatively desirable to hold. If, and if so, how exactly such peer network effects appear is at the heart of this report. It has been suggested in other areas that in particular strong ties in networks contribute to spreading knowledge and new ideas (Collar, 2022) and we suggest that strong ties, in other words close friends, if equipped with skills, are important mechanisms to spread these within the network. Such mechanisms are rather unexplored for youth digital skills, however.

2.2 Peer networks

Social networks are characterised by ties between individuals. Such ties can be stronger or weaker or even completely absent within a given social structure. Taking the example of the social structure of a school class, some students will have strong ties with certain others, while having only weak relationships or even hardly any to no interaction with other students. Hence, tie strengths between students differ, even within a school class. Schools, workplaces, or voluntary organisations – which give rise to peer networks – tend to create social contexts that are characterised by a high degree of social separation, for instance based on gender, ethnicity, age, or religion (McPherson et al., 2001). In such cases people generally have a tendency to form what is called homophilous social relationships (Feld, 1981; McPherson et al., 2001). The notion of homophily, or “friends tend to be much more similar than chance alone would predict” (Lewis, Gonzalez, & Kaufman, 2012, p. 68), refers to the tendency of people to associate with each other based on certain attributes or traits. When such traits are based on socio-demographic factors, the literature refers to demographic homophily (Huckfeldt & Sprague, 1995; Lazer et al., 2010; Marsden, 1987; McPherson et al., 2001). In addition

to demographic homophily, the notion of value homophily (McPherson et al., 2001) suggests that individuals naturally gravitate towards attitudinally similar others while avoiding counter-attitudinal interactions (Mutz, 2006; Ulbig & Funk 1999). While in this report we are not interested in exploring the notions of demographic or attitudinal homophily, it is important to note that peer networks and differential ties within school classes are unlikely to form in a random manner.

While the intuitive notion of homophily is regarded as one of the strongest predictors of how children and adolescents may actively construct their social relationships, we are now turning to the literature from the field of political communication to draw an alternative scenario that may be relevant to apply also in the context of digital skills. Social network studies on political communication have emphasised that expertise of others is one of the important selection criteria of political interactions (e.g., Huckfeldt, 2001; Huckfeldt, Pietryka & Reilly, 2014; McClurg, 2006). Those who are politically knowledgeable are regarded as high-quality informants within social networks (McClurg, 2006). This provides strong incentives for an individual to turn towards such knowledgeable others to reduce information costs when seeking information (Pietryka, 2016). Available evidence in representative sample surveys (Huckfeldt, 2001) as well as in controlled experiments (Huckfeldt et al., 2014) supports this perspective, and this relationship appears to be very robust, even in the context of political disagreement. More generally, peer networks provide important opportunity structure, such that physical and social proximity of two actors in peer networks is associated with interpersonal influence between those two actors (Masden & Friedkin, 1993). It partly does so by providing easily available sources of obtaining and exchanging relevant information (“informational influence”: Deutsch & Gerard, 1955; Price, Nir & Cappella, 2006), as indicated in two-step flow hypothesis, opinion leadership, and diffusion of innovation (Burt, 1999; Coleman, Katz & Menzel, 1957). In this regard, expertise of one’s network ties – all else being equal – are likely to be regarded as one of the important drivers of peer-to-peer interactions in this regard (Downs, 1957). Translated to the context of this report, we can thus assume that expertise – that is high levels of digital skills – may matter for the formation and maintenance of network ties. However, expertise is likely to matter more strongly in contexts in which obtaining digital skills is normatively desirable. Hence, students would have incentives to seek expertise.

Another context within which peer networks might systematically govern the acquisition and maintenance of digital skills is normative pressure that would arise from one’s network, in terms of behavioural norms and expectations of others. Youth might for instance be peer pressured into using certain platforms in which everyone communicates or undertake certain online activities because most others are seemingly doing so. For such normative influences within social networks to be effective, a clear delineation of the reference group is a prerequisite for an individual’s perception of the punitive consequences when his or her actions deviate from the norm of such a group (Shulman & Levine, 2012). Human behaviour is, at least in parts, driven by a desire to seek potential social rewards (for conformity) or to avoid social sanctions (for noncompliance) associated with the socially prescribed modes of behaviour (Friedkin, 2004; Lapinski & Rimal, 2005). It is suggested that densely connected ego-networks enable coordination of behaviours with others and, therefore, reinforce social norms (Gargiulo & Benassi, 2000). In such closed, highly interconnected networks, actors are more easily able to monitor one another’s attributes (Friedkin, 1983) and collectively coordinate their actions than in open or disconnected networks (Burt, 2000; Coleman, 1990). Therefore, actors embedded in such social relations are more likely to conform to the norms or expectations of others (e.g., Gargiulo & Benassi, 2000). It may be that such dynamics also apply in the context of digital skills expertise in school class environments.

Given the lack of systematic network approaches in the extant literature on youth digital skills, yet some empirical evidence regarding peer effects, we attempt to translate some of the insights discussed

above, that largely stem from studies of political communication in peer networks, to the context of interest in this report. *First*, we will engage with the question whether expertise explains homophily in peer networks. In other words, **will peers with similar levels of digital skills be more likely to show ties in a peer network?** To contextualise this, we will also look at other factors, both socio-demographic (gender, socio-economic status) and expertise (school performance), in relation to homophily. *Second*, we will investigate the relationship between the structural network characteristics and individual characteristics. Here we specifically ask **whether giving advice about digital technology to others in the peer network or receiving advice from others is related to holding better developed digital skills?** Both questions will allow us to take the first steps towards a better understanding of how peer networks are related to digital skills, alongside other individual-level or social context factors.

2.3 Network data

To our knowledge, there is only a very limited number of studies in the field of children's and adolescents' ICT use in relation to digital skills that would employ a social network data approach. Even in more general terms, extant studies dealing with peer networks have relied on cross-sectional surveys that are based on name-generator and name-interpreter techniques (see Eveland et al., 2012; Klofstad, McClurg & Rolfe, 2009 for a brief review). It is, however, difficult to distinguish the causal relationship between individual attributes and social network using purely cross-sectional, traditional sample survey data (e.g., Shalizi & Thomas, 2011; Steglich et al., 2010).

Existing studies of egocentric social network data heavily rely on analyses using ego-alter dyads as the unit of analysis while treating each of the dyads as an independent observation. Such practices do neither fully account for all possible aspects of a broad network structure outside of an ego's direct social contacts, they also fail to address unobserved feedback, including any higher-order endogenous mechanisms between network structures and behaviours (Burk, Steglich & Snijders, 2007; Steglich et al., 2010). Moreover, when network data are concerned, traditional statistical techniques cannot be applied to evaluate baseline probabilities because this violates the fundamental assumption of statistical independence (Burk et al., 2007).

Furthermore, the proper identification of social selection effects requires not only information between connected dyads, but also critically hinges on information between unconnected dyads (Steglich et al., 2010). Typical egocentric network data cannot provide such information. Also, most of the egocentric network data limits the number of potential alters named by a focal respondent to up to three to five individuals (fixed choice design: Marsden, 1987), which is more likely to elicit "strong tie" networks and therefore likely to capture a small, focused subset of alters (Marin, 2004; Marsden, 2005). This could have important implications for the robustness of the statistical analysis, as it cannot effectively address other plausible alternative explanations based on more complex mutual interdependencies inherent in network data

This analytical challenge has led to the view that it is necessary to study the coevolution of a individual's attributes and social networks using two or more waves of whole-network panel data (Lazer et al., 2010; Snijders et al., 2006; Steglich et al., 2010). The ySKILLS survey data go a long way into this direction, attempting to follow the pioneering work of Snijders (2001) and Lazer et al. (2010). Within the confines of a sample of individual school classes the project has collected unique sociocentric network data that allow the identification of characteristics of egos and alters and selected ties.

3 Data and analysis

In this chapter we aim to provide three particular insights into our unique ySKILLS network survey data. First, we provide detailed information on measurements used. Second, we approach the problem of missing data in our student networks. Third, we elaborate on different analysis techniques to apply to our data. Readers interested in the substantial result only can easily skip the methodological background provided in the second and third points.

3.1 The ySKILLS network data

To our knowledge, it is the first time that a school children survey across different countries and schools makes use of our network data approach. The resulting data set is unique in the sense that it does specify networks within classes and allows for an identification of characteristics of both egos and alters within the networks. In this report we rely on data from the first wave only, given the complexities involved in the analysis of the data (as elaborated below) and given ongoing identification issues between wave 1 and wave 2 data. For general information about the survey and the questionnaire for the first wave of data collection, please consult [ySKILLS D4.1](#).

Our approach was to collect our sociometric (i.e., full network as opposed to egocentric) network data in the framework of school classes. Every individual student in a class was known beforehand and hence was part of the possible network. This makes our network data quite unique. Overall, our data have several hierarchical levels (classes, schools, and countries), allowing us to compare how partial pooling of estimates works on multiple clustering levels (unlike only on the network level as has been done previously). Furthermore, the data offer a collection of sociocentric networks (in contrast to egocentric networks), networks that have a known boundary and with data on all nodes and in the population of interest. Compared to the more commonplace egocentric networks, sociocentric networks provide a much more accurate estimation for Exponential Random Graph Models (ERGMs) (e.g., Krivitsky et al., 2021).

Given the constraints of a school survey and the fact that the overall survey required the measurement of a great range of different variables and concepts related to digital skills, their antecedents and their outcomes, we restricted the network data collection to a maximum of three outgoing ties. In other words, students were asked to name up to three friends within their class that they felt closest to (“Name three of your closest friends in your classroom.”). This is also based on the consideration that network ties elicited for each adolescent would reflect a rather stable, long-term social relationship that may register strong enough in someone's cognitive memory, and therefore this approach is less likely to create recall bias as is common in the roster method for the collection of sociocentric or complete network data. To anonymise the data collection while at the same time allowing for the identification of concrete individuals, a list of nicknames was provided that contained all students in the class and nicknames were used for this name generation task (for details see [ySKILLS D4.1](#)). Now for each of these three friends, students were asked to answer four questions, which (1) specify the strength of the relationship between the students (tie strength), (2) provide a subjective estimate about the friends perceived digital skills (expertise, (3) digital skills advice seeking, and (4) digital skills advice giving.

- (1) During this school year, how often do you spend time with [Friend 1, 2, 3] in your free time (online or offline)?
- (2) How good do you think [Friend 1, 2, 3] is at using the internet and technologies such as mobile phones?
- (3) During this school year, how often did you ask [Friend 1, 2, 3] for help with using the internet and technologies such as mobile phones?

- (4) During this school year, how often did [Friend 1, 2, 3] ask you for help with using the internet and technologies such as mobile phones?

Our models presented below are substantially based on these network variables, but also include an array of control variables, such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, etc. For details on the measurement of these variables, please consult [ySKILLS D4.1](#). The data contains information on 123 networks (school classes), nested in 15 different schools, across three of the six ySKILLS focal countries (i.e., Germany, Italy, and Portugal). The data were collected across middle and high schools — age range from 12 to 20 ($M_{\text{age}} = 14.96$; $SD_{\text{age}} = 1.26$). The number of nodes ranged from 5 to 32 nodes ($M = 20.82$; $SD = 6.30$); The average in-degree of the networks was $M_{\text{in-degree}} = 2.35$; $SD_{\text{in-degree}} = .44$.

One aspect that became obvious after first inspections of the data is that hardly any of the networks had complete data. Missing data is of course a common problem in survey research, yet for our network approach, missing data adds additional complexity, as elaborated below.

3.2 Missing Network Data in Multiple Complete Networks

Missing data are posing a significant challenge to the reliable estimation of true social network-based impacts. In social network analysis, however, missing data may create even bigger problems than in conventional frameworks such as linear models. Since network data are relational by definition, a single missing data point may introduce bias both to the immediate network neighbourhood as well as to the full network structure, thus seriously increasing the bias of statistical estimation. Additionally, the inherent complexity of network data means that missing data are more likely to occur in the data collection process than in the conventional designs, exacerbating the problem of missing data even more. Another issue with missing data in social network analysis is that it can lead to inaccurate conclusions about the properties of the network, such as its size, density, or centrality measures. This is because missing data points can affect the calculation of these measures, resulting in a skewed understanding of the network.

There are a range of reasons why missing data would be more plausible than otherwise in our network data. Non-response is the major culprit in social network missing data. Non-response can manifest itself in item non-response (i.e., missing attribute information) or unit non-response (i.e., missing nodes and all potential ties of that node). Two further structural types of missing data can be present: tie variables (i.e., connections between actors), or node attributes (e.g., age of a participant), and they require different imputation methods. All of these scenarios have some nonzero likelihood to occur in our data. Students missing a day of school would result in a unit non-response and many students missing on the day that the survey was administered would result in highly biased network estimates. Students not understanding a question and therefore deciding to skip part of the questionnaire may be another reason for missing data, resulting in missing nodal attributes. This leads to the fact that, in wave 1, about 99 per cent of the individual class networks show some patterns of missing data, and hence the need for seriously addressing the issue.

A common procedure to deal with missing data is the imputation of missing values. Given the potential biases occurring through missing data, it is argued that pursuing missing value imputation would be beneficial for our analyses. Yet there is not just one universally agreed upon way to impute missing network data. We show how the various types of missing data outlined above can be handled with using different data imputation techniques, and provide general recommendations for dealing with missings in our network data. We do so, by drawing on a simulation scenario.

To assess the consequences of missing values in our networks for our estimates, it is important to know what the “correct” population estimates were, and to compare estimation results based on networks with different types of missing data imputation methods to those correct estimates. Given that we have almost no networks without any missing data, the best way to establish correct estimates is to artificially generate a network which we then take as the correct one. Subsequently we would synthetically impose missing data to that network, so that we have one complete network and can compare different types of networks with missing data to that complete network. In a next step we then impute the missing data based on different types of imputation methods or data removals. Concretely we look at three different ways to deal with missing.

- (1) *Node Removal*. The method of removing nodes with missing data from the network is a form of data cleaning where any nodes that have missing information are removed from the network before analysis. This method, however, is likely to introduce bias to the network estimation because of the relational structure of the data.
- (2) *Imputing Median value*. Median value imputation is a method of handling missing data in which the missing values are replaced with the median value of the non-missing observations in the same feature. This method is often used when the data is missing at random and the distribution of the feature is not normal. The median value is chosen as it is a robust statistic that is not affected by outliers in the data.
- (3) *Multiple imputation*. Multiple imputation (also known as model-based imputation) is a method of handling missing data that uses statistical models to generate multiple imputed datasets to account for the uncertainty in the missing data. In this method, a model is fit to the non-missing data and then used to generate multiple plausible imputed datasets for the missing data. These imputed datasets are then analysed separately, and the results are combined to account for the uncertainty introduced by the missing data. This method can be more complex to implement than simpler methods such as mean or median imputation, but it can provide more accurate results by accounting for the uncertainty in the missing data. The most common method for this is called "Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations" (MICE) which uses multiple regression models to impute missing data.

We estimate the complete networks and the networks in which missing data have been treated differently and then calculate Mean Absolute Error between the initial and the imputed data. This procedure is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. VISUALISATION OF THE SIMULATION PROCEDURE

For our simulation runs we specify different scenarios in which we vary the size of the networks (ranging from 20 to 60 nodes), the number of covariates of the nodes (ranging from 2 to 6) and, most importantly, the amount of missing data (ranging from 5 to 15 per cent) and different techniques to deal with the missing (that is removal, median value imputation and multiple imputation). The combination of these yields a total of 8,100 different scenarios for the comparisons. The simulation setups are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. SIMULATION PARAMETERS			
Network Size (Nodes)	20	40	60
Number of Nodal Covariates	2	4	6
% Missing	5 %	10 %	15 %
Imputation Technique	Removal	Median Value	Multiple Imputation

The results of these simulations are quite clear and provide a rather consistent picture. Figures 3 a–c present the mean absolute error between the correct estimates and the estimates based on the different imputation models, where higher values indicate a stronger divergence from the correct estimate. The first panel (panel a) shows the result for 5 per cent, panel (b) for 10 percent and panel (c) for 15 per cent missing data that were imputed (or removed).

Figure 3a. SIMULATION RESULTS 5% OF NODES WITH MISSING DATA

Figure 3b. SIMULATION RESULTS 10% OF NODES WITH MISSING DATA

Figure 3c. SIMULATION RESULTS 15% OF NODES WITH MISSING DATA

Across all Panels it becomes evident that multiple imputation is the best option for imputing missing data. As could be expected, simply removing the nodes with missing data leads to the largest bias in the estimates, while multiple imputation consistently gives the most correct estimates. Yet, the results strongly depend on the ratio of missing values in the data. If networks have 15 per cent missings, the estimation results are generally far off the correct values, no matter which imputation method was used (see panel c). For networks with less missings of only 5 per cent, the difference between removal and imputations becomes quite large and substantial, while in this scenario the difference between median and multiple imputation is less strong. Given that the average ratio of missingness in the first wave ySKILLS network data is around 9%, it seems most advisable to use multiple imputation as an imputation technique (see Panel b). We, however, also would like to note that multiple imputations are much more computationally demanding than median imputations.

3.3 Dealing with Multiple Networks

Exponential Random Graph models (ERGM) are gaining popularity in the social sciences, since they allow modelling the endogenous structural characteristics of the network (i.e., mutuals or triangles, etc.) simultaneously with the effect of exogenous variables (i.e., gender, skills, etc.). The ERGM framework is generally limited to estimating the parameters of a single network and the vast majority of studies involving ERGMs focus either on a specific single network or a small set of independent networks that are compared/contrasted in the study (see Lusher et al., 2013). Nevertheless, such an approach does provide valuable information about the structure and social processes within a specific setting, but it inevitably leaves the question of whether the structural effects obtained from the model pertain only to this specific network, or whether these structures are actually generalisable to a wider set of networks in a relatively similar context.

In recent years, collections of multiple networks have become somewhat more commonplace, with studies focusing on multiple networks simultaneously to investigate broader structural phenomena (e.g., Lubbers, 2003; Lubbers & Snijders, 2007; Eveland & Kleinman, 2013; Goodreau et al., 2009; Song, 2015; Minozzi et al., 2020). In essence, this multiple networks or multilevel approach is characterised as a set of N nodes (e.g., people), broken down into K separate blocks (e.g., schools) such that edges E (e.g., social network ties) within a block A_k are dependent on each other, but are independent of edges in other A blocks (subnetworks) (Lazega & Snijders, 2015; Schweinberger & Handcock, 2015). Thus, the need for an analytic framework capable of dealing with such clustered structure, or a ‘population’ (Lehmann & White, 2021) of networks, has become more evident. This applies to the ySKILLS network data as well, given that we have collected a vast number of smaller, class-based networks clustered within schools and countries.

Several estimation methods were proposed to deal with this structure. For example, Lubbers and Snijders (2007) investigated the variance in structural characteristics between 57 school classes. They proposed a “two-step regression” approach to analyse the estimates from multiple networks to determine their general significance. This approach is essentially a meta-analysis with a known level-1 variation (Goldstein, 2011; see also Snijders & Baerveldt, 2003). This approach was further improved by estimating a multilevel hierarchical Bayesian model to incorporate a partial pooling of the estimates across networks (Minozzi et al., 2020). This, however, is not the only possible way to deal with multiple networks. A different approach to multiple (multilevel) network estimation is the single holistic estimation or “integrated” approach (e.g., Snijders, 2016), in which the whole population is estimated as a single network, but with structural zeros imposed in such a way that actors across subpopulations (i.e., individual networks) cannot interact between themselves. Unlike the previously described meta-analytic paradigm, this is a one-step solution to the estimation problem. While both procedures are generally thought to be significantly superior than estimating ERGMs one-by-one (or even simply investigating a singular network, as has been the predominant modus operandi when dealing with ERGMs), they both are a relatively recent addition to social network analysis. To our knowledge, they have not been systematically and empirically compared with one another, and no specific advantages or drawbacks of either have been outlined. Before moving into an analysis of our ySKILLS network data, there was the need to come to a systematic understanding of the value of both approaches.

In what follows in a brief description below (for a more elaborate account see Tolochko and Boomgaarden, (2022)) we systematically compare the aforementioned methods of multiple network estimation by using our ySKILLS dataset (Study 1) as well as simulation modelling (Study 2).

3.3.1 Estimation of the ySKILLS data (Study 1)¹

The first step is to find the set of model specifications (network statistics) that works for all empirical networks in the data. This is an iterative process – once the parametrisation that is applicable to all

¹ The analyses for this project are done in R, with an ERGM modelling toolkit package (Hunter et al., 2008). Next, the `mlegm` (Stewart & Schweinberger, 2018) is used for the “integrated”, supernetwork estimation. Finally, Stan statistical

networks has been found, the goodness of fit is obtained for all networks. This process is repeated until the goodness of fit is acceptable. As mentioned above, we consider two general methods of modelling – *Hierarchical* (i.e., a meta-analytic hierarchical regression model) and *Integrated* (estimation of the whole supernetwork). Furthermore, the hierarchical approach can accommodate additional grouping, therefore we break it down to a *simple hierarchical* method – with standard errors clustered only on the network level, and *grouped hierarchical* method – with standard errors clustered on the network *and* country level.

Here we present the results obtained by the different methods of estimation (hierarchical with no country grouping, hierarchical with country grouping, and integrated). The posterior modes and 95% Credibility Intervals (for the Integrated approach, the 95% Confidence Interval is presented) are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. POSTERIOR MODES AND 95% CONFIDENCE INTERVALS

As can be seen from Figure 4, $\hat{\theta}$'s (individual network parameters) for two hierarchical approaches are very close to each other, albeit the model that incorporates group variance has significantly wider CIs. On the other hand, $\hat{\theta}$ obtained with the integrated approach is consistently different from the first two – either significantly lower (in the case of θ_0 and θ_2), or higher (in the case of θ_1 and θ_4). Moreover, in three out of four cases, the CIs of the Integrated approach do not even overlap with the wider CIs of the hierarchical group model estimates. While all of these parameter estimates agree with each other in terms of their direction of effects (i.e., showing the same sign), nevertheless, the differences are large enough to draw different conclusions in a hypothesis-testing scenario.

modelling language (Carpenter et al., 2017) and the BRMS package (Bürkner, 2017) are used for the Bayesian multilevel modelling.

Additionally, we can look at the estimated τ parameters (network and group variance) from the hierarchical models to understand whether the spread in the network and/or group estimates is indeed warranted. Figure 5 shows that both the network and the country (group) variances are quite substantial. Importantly, the group variances are actually different for different θ parameters, indicating that including the group information into the model may be beneficial, especially if one intends to predict, for example, specific group effects.

Figure 5. POSTERIOR DISTRIBUTION OF VARIANCES

3.3.2 Monte-Carlo Simulation (Study 2)

The study conducts a simulation to evaluate the performance of different methods for estimating network parameters. By creating a scenario in which the true parameters are known, the researchers can see which method estimates them most accurately. This is important as it is not possible to know the true parameters with certainty in real-world situations.

The simulation uses the exponential graph modelling framework to simulate networks with chosen parameters such as network size, density, and number of triangles. The chosen parameters are referred to as "ground truth" and the estimated parameters are referred to as "estimated parameters." The ground truth parameters are created by selecting specific values for μ (overall mean) and group effect Δ_j . The simulated networks are then estimated using different methods, such as the ERGM simulation algorithm, and the results are compared to the ground truth parameters to see how well they were estimated.

The simulation considers different scenarios such as the number of groups, the size of the groups, the number of nodes in a single network, and the group effect size. All the simulation runs are replicated several times with different parameters. For each run, the absolute error ($|\hat{\theta} - \theta|$) is calculated. The results of the simulation will be used to determine which method is the most accurate at estimating

the true parameters, and which simulation factors have the strongest impact on the accuracy of the estimates. Table 2 below provides the simulation scenarios for the study.

Table 2. MONTE-CARLO SIMULATION INPUT PARAMETERS

Simulation Factors	Simulation Parameters
K (Number of Groups)	1, 3, 5
S_k (Group Size)	10 (small), 20 (medium), 30 (large)
N_{nodes} (Nodes per Network)	20 (small), 30 (medium), 40 (large)
δ_j (Group Effect Size)	.1 (small), .3 (medium), .6 (large)

Figure 6 presents the results of the simulation runs in terms of the absolute error (AE), defined as $\Delta\theta = |\hat{\theta} - \theta|$. Three columns represent θ_0, θ_1 , and θ_2 , respectively. Separate panels are broken down into the number of groups for the simulation run, while the three rows represent the other three simulation factors. “H”, “HG”, and “I” stand for “Hierarchical”, “Hierarchical-Group”, and “Integrated”. Hierarchical-Group is omitted from the single group condition.

As can be seen from the simulation results, the absolute error is, unsurprisingly, very small for single group conditions across all models and simulation factors. The absolute error, nevertheless, begins to increase with the number of groups and the group effect size, which represents the degree of heterogeneity across groups. This pattern is the most pronounced for the Integrated estimation method since it appears that it struggles to estimate the between-group variability. The hierarchical models are less affected by the number of groups and the group effect size. The increase in group size and the number of nodes per network are allowing for a more precise estimation, but only for the hierarchical models; the integrated model is not affected by these factors.

The simulation study was conducted to evaluate the mean absolute error (MAE) of different estimation methods based on different combinations of simulation factors. The results of the study indicate that the MAE estimates are consistently lowest for the hierarchical group models, for every simulation factor. The hierarchical models without the grouped random errors also performed well, but the difference between grouped and non-grouped models is "statistically significant." The integrated method performed on par with the hierarchical method only in the single group scenario. For the integrated method, estimation error increases more sharply as the number of groups gets higher and as the group effect increases than for the other two estimation methods. The increase in group size, as well as network size, helps all estimation methods to achieve better accuracy.

The simulation results, as shown in Figure 6, indicate that the estimation method based on a hierarchical regression model (with errors clustered on the group level) was the most accurate, with the smallest mean absolute error across all conditions. The hierarchical model with no grouping came in a close second. The integrated model was the least accurate, with the largest mean absolute error across all conditions. The number of groups and the group effect size were the two most important factors influencing the mean absolute error. Increasing the number of networks and the size of networks decreased the absolute error.

Figure 6. SIMULATION RESULTS

And, predictably, increasing the number of networks and the size of networks will decrease the absolute error. At face value, it would seem like the hierarchical models are an easy method to recommend to a researcher dealing with multiple networks, given the lowest estimation error. Nevertheless, several practical considerations are not immediately apparent from the results that may impact the choice of the method.

We recommend that if the data is known to come from different distributions and there is information on the group affiliation of each individual network – the hierarchical grouped approach is the optimal choice. Nevertheless, hierarchical models without the group information also provide fairly accurate results and should be the preferred choice in a study setup where grouping information is not available (which is probably the vast majority of scenarios) therefore researchers are not a priori assuming a particular population distribution. Finally, the integrated approach should be chosen only in those situations, where the researcher is fairly confident that the data come from the same underlying distribution (no significant group effects, which is quite a strong assumption to make). The ease of estimation of the integrated models wins over the marginal increase in accuracy provided by the hierarchical models for one group scenario.

Based on the methodological considerations presented above, we would first impute missing values by means of a multiple imputation approach. Then our analytical approach to the ySKILLS data (when dealing with the ERGM methodology) is to model each individual network separately, and then pool the estimates with a hierarchical regression model to properly model estimate uncertainty. This is done in a similar fashion to pooling estimates in a meta-analysis (e.g., Lubbers & Snijders, 2007; Song, 2015). When dealing with the descriptive social network analysis (as is the case in the Results section below), we have taken a sample-based approach by simultaneously considering multiple networks to provide a more comprehensive analysis. This methodology enables us to draw broader conclusions and generalise our findings to other similar contexts. Additionally, analysing

social networks as a sample is important for obtaining more robust findings and increasing the external validity of our research.

4 Results

4.1 Descriptive Network Analyses

Each observational unit of a peer network (in our data a school classroom) provides information on three qualitatively different types of relationships: friendship relationships, advice *giving* relationships, and advice *seeking* relationships. For illustrative purposes, a sample of empirical networks is provided in Figure 7, based on the initial friends networks. Although only illustrative in nature and only capturing a small sample of our networks, it can be seen that in some classes we find very dispersed and clearly defined sub-networks that have no inter-relationships. In other classes the networks are more dense and interconnected. In what follows below, we will capture some of these differences more quantitatively.

Figure 7. SAMPLE OF NETWORKS

The network size ranges from 5 to 32 nodes ($SD = 6.30$) for all three network types, hence we have school classes with networks consisting of minimum 5 and maximum 32 students. The degree distribution, that is the total amount of ties between nodes that a network consists of is ($M = 49.20$; $SD = 17.69$) for the friendship networks, ($M = 24.83$; $SD = 10.19$) for the advice-giving networks, and ($M = 22.00$; $SD = 9.15$) for the advice-seeking networks. Figures 8a and b provide more detailed descriptive statistics about our networks. In the context of advice-giving and advice-seeking networks within school classes, the degree distribution and network size can provide important insights into the dynamics and interactions within the class. A highly skewed degree distribution in advice-giving networks, for example, could indicate that there are several students who are frequently sought after for advice and are actively providing advice to their peers. This could be a positive indicator of a strong and supportive peer group or the presence of “super helper” within the class. In contrast, a dispersed degree distribution in advice-seeking networks could indicate that students are not

frequently seeking multiple advice from their peers (beyond some help from those who are central in the advice-giving network), which may suggest a lack of institutionalised support or a lack of generalised trust in the peer group.

Figure 8a. DEGREE DISTRIBUTION OF EMPIRICAL CLASSROOM NETWORKS

Figure 8b. IN-DEGREE DISTRIBUTION OF EMPIRICAL CLASSROOM NETWORKS

4.2 Homophily and Assortativity

As discussed further above, a certain degree of homophily is expected to occur in class networks. Homophily is a network property that describes a structural tendency of nodes to form connections between each other based on a similarity of their attributes. In other words, we can ascertain whether for instance students who share certain demographic characteristics tend to form stronger interconnections within a network. One measure of network homophily is assortativity. It is a measure of the tendency of network nodes to attach to each other based on some shared property or an attribute (for example, gender, socio-economic status, etc.). This specific measurement ranges from -1 to 1 indicating either a negative correlation between a tie and some attribute (-1) or a positive correlation (1). Similarly to the correlation coefficient, if there is no dependence between attributes, assortativity is 0.

As was emphasised in the methods section, it is important to consider not just individual networks, but also multiple networks as a sample. This allows for the examination of patterns and trends across different groups or contexts, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics at play. The unique data obtained in the ySKILLS project allow us to do exactly that.

In line with the question provided further above, we now consider whether **socio-demographic factors** tend to explain stronger clusters within networks. More importantly, we also consider whether school performance and digital skills levels bring people more closely together. Hence, we present the results of assortativity based on several individual attributes: gender, socio-economic status, school performance, and proficiency in digital skills for the three different types of network relations (friendship, advice giving and advice seeking), all illustrated in Figure 9, panels a to c.

Figure 9a. ASSORTATIVITY BASED ON VARIOUS ATTRIBUTES (FRIENDSHIP NETWORKS)

Figure 9b. ASSORTATIVITY BASED ON VARIOUS ATTRIBUTES (ADVICE-SEEKING NETWORKS)

Advice Seeking Networks

Figure 9c. ASSORTATIVITY BASED ON VARIOUS ATTRIBUTES (ADVICE-GIVING NETWORKS)

Advice Giving Networks

The three panels of Figure 9 show the distribution of the assortativity metric across three different types of networks and different nodal attributes across 123 separate networks. As can be seen from the figures, the attribute that has the strongest effect on the tie formation is *gender* (lower left panel of Figure 9c). Gender is positively correlated with tie formation across all three types of relationships (i.e., friendship, advice seeking, and advice giving), which indicates that students of the same gender tend to disproportionately be friends with each other, tend to ask advice in matters of digital technology from the same gender, as well as seek advice from the same gender. All other attributes do not have such a strong effect on tie formation.

Socio-economic status, for example, does not have a statistically significant effect on tie formation in any of the relationship types. Hence, we do not see that students from similar backgrounds would build strong clusters within their classes. *School performance* has a very weak yet statistically significant² *negative* relationship in the *advice-giving* and *advice-seeking* networks, indicating that in a pair of students, where one is asking for advice, or giving an advice to another, there is a (very slightly) higher probability that these students will differ in school performance. As such, there is some suggestive evidence that network ties also form based on expertise, as discussed further above. Interestingly and contrary to the results for school performance, for the proficiency in digital skills we find a very weak positive effect in both the *advice-giving* and *advice-seeking* networks, indicating that students tend to ask for advice and seek advice from other students with *similar* proficiency in digital skills. This may indicate the possibility that advice giving and advice seeking are by nature characterised by seeking social approval and confirmation. Nevertheless, both the school performance and digital skills, while being statistically significant, affect network assortativity only slightly. More complex models are required to investigate this effect in more detail.

4.3 Peer network antecedents of digital skills

Regarding our second research question, we now examine the relationship between structural networks characteristics and individual characteristics. More specifically, we now look at the influence of peers on different dimensions of digital skills. To this end, a combination of survey data and network data is used in a series of regression models.

Dependent variables. Proficiency in digital skills is used as the dependent variable for the model. As described at length in [ySKILLS D2.1](#), technical/operational skills, programming, information navigation/processing skills, communication/interaction, content creation/production skills and digital knowledge, as well as a combination of all skills are used in the regression model as separate dependent variables.

Independent variables. These are extracted from the structural network characteristics in our network data. Specifically, the structural variables are: Average time spent with friends, calculated as the average of the incoming (In) and outgoing (Out) tie strengths; average advice seeking, calculated as the average incoming (In) and outgoing (Out) value in advice-seeking ties networks. Finally, average advice giving was calculated as the average incoming (In) and outgoing (Out) value of advice-giving networks.

Control variables. These are Gender, Age, Socio-economic status, School performance, Time spent online (general), Time spent online (learning), Time spent online (entertainment), Restrictive parental

² Statistical significance was determined by generating random networks of similar size and density and performing a two-sampled t-test between the empirical and the simulated distributions.

mediation, Enabling parental mediation, Family environment, Friends support, and Classroom support were used. For the measurement of these variables, please consult [ySKILLS D4.1](#).

Model. Each independent variable was modelled using a hierarchical Bayesian regression model. The standard errors were clustered on Country (N=3), School (N=15), and Class (N=138). Each model used the same sample with an N = 2385 students included.

The posterior distributions from the models are presented in Figures 10 (panels a through f) below (in the context of these models, they can be interpreted as beta-coefficients from an OLS regression model). As clearly demonstrated, the structural characteristics of the network have a significant impact on the majority of skills. The effects observed here are consistent with what could reasonably be expected. When a student frequently seeks advice from peers and receives a lot of advice from others, his skill level in that particular area is likely to be lower. In contrast, when a student is often asked for advice and often gives advice to peers, his skill level in that area is likely to be rated higher. These effects are most pronounced for technical skills and are relatively minimal for communication skills. However, it should be noted that this pattern applies to all types of digital skills, regardless of the specific skill considered.

Figure 10a. POSTERIOR DISTRIBUTION OF PARAMETERS (TECHNICAL SKILLS MODEL)

Figure 10b. POSTERIOR DISTRIBUTION OF PARAMETERS (PROGRAMMING SKILLS MODEL)

Figure 10c. POSTERIOR DISTRIBUTION OF PARAMETERS (COMMUNICATION SKILLS MODEL)

Figure 10d. POSTERIOR DISTRIBUTION OF PARAMETERS (CONTENT CREATION SKILLS MODEL)

Figure 10e. POSTERIOR DISTRIBUTION OF PARAMETERS (KNOWLEDGE SKILLS MODEL)

Figure 10f. POSTERIOR DISTRIBUTION OF PARAMETERS (COMBINED SKILLS MODEL)

This pattern of network effects is also shown for the total skills variable, which is an additive index of all individual skills. It should also be noted that only for the advice giving and advice seeking networks do we find significant effects. The friend networks themselves are unrelated in all cases. In addition to the network effects, we also see quite consistent pictures regarding the control variables in our model. For most cases (except for programming) time spent online in general, but also for different types of activities, is positively related to holding good digital skills. More interestingly for our focus on social context effects, we see that parental mediation, no matter whether restricting or enabling, does not show any significant relationship with skills in most models. Only for technical skills there is a slight negative relationship with restrictive parental mediation. Although our peer network effects are not particularly strong, they seem to perform better in terms of social context effect than parental mediation. Other indicators of family environment show a rather mixed picture at best, while having a support circle of friends appears to be overall rather positively correlated with digital skills overall. Interestingly, students' cognitive resources are also not consistently correlated with digital skills.

5. Conclusion and implications

This report provides some first insights into the unique type of peer network data that were collected in the framework of the ySKILLS school survey. We set out arguing that for a better understanding of how social contexts shape the development of digital skills we would need to pay more systematic attention to the influence from peers. To that end, the ySKILLS project collected unique sociocentric network data in a range of school classes across different schools and countries. We wondered whether expertise in digital skills would structure networks and whether network structures in terms of giving advice to or seeking advice from others in relation to digital skills would be related to students' proficiency in digital skills.

Towards the unique and new data, we described two important methodological considerations and analyses. First, we discussed how to deal with missing data in a network approach and showed that, in particular for networks such as those collected within ySKILLS, multiple imputation techniques would be most appropriate for dealing with missing data. Second, we show how best to analyse such network data from multiple small networks, using a hierarchical analysis approach with group-level clustered errors. These methodological discussions were fundamental to appropriately start the more substantial analyses.

Related to our central questions, we first note that homophily in the peer network was to some extent, though not very strongly, structured by expertise. Young people with similar levels of digital skills were more likely to form advice-giving and advice-seeking ties with each other. However, this was different for school performance, another indicator of expertise, where we found that advice network ties were more common between children or young people with different levels of school performance. Both factors are clearly outweighed by socio-demographic factors, with gender standing out as very strongly structuring network ties, with boys forming ties with boys and girls with girls.

More importantly, we were able to show that giving advice or seeking peer networks is systematically related to digital skills in a theoretically expected manner. If a student often seeks advice from their peers and receives a high amount of advice from others, it is likely that their skill level in that particular area will be lower. In contrast, if a student is often asked for advice and frequently provides advice to their peers, it is likely that their skill level in that particular area is higher. So, on the one hand, students seem to be well aware of their own level of expertise relative to others in their school network and seek and accept advice when their level of expertise is low. On the other hand, it appears that expertise can spread in the classroom due to the presence of a few skilled individuals.

In summary, we see a picture in which students' digital skill levels determine the formation of network ties, both in terms of friendship in general but also in terms of giving and seeking advice. At the same time, asking and giving advice are systematically related to skills, in the sense that asking and receiving advice does correlate with lower levels of digital skills, and giving advice and being asked with higher levels of digital skills.

Our analyses are only a first step towards a better understanding of network influences. In subsequent analyses, we will focus on more advanced models, which better account for network structures and for dynamics over time, to better understand the causal mechanisms behind the relationships observed here.

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